

Influence of Livelihood Assets in Watermelon Production in Sokoto State, Nigeria

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This study was conducted to analyze the influence of livelihoods assets in watermelon production in Sokoto state. Structured questionnaire and focus group discussion checklist were used in collecting data from 480 watermelon farmers. Multistage sampling technique was used to arrive at the sample size of the study. Frequency, percentage and pair wise ranking were used to analyze the data. The findings reveal that most (59.2%) of the watermelon farmers are within the age range of 40-49 years, majorities (95.4%) were male with low family size of 1-5 persons. While, (48.3%) of the farmers have experience in watermelon production of 11-15 years. The result further reveals that majority (70.6%) of the farmers participate in watermelon production by using their personal saving. It indicated that Less than half 44.8% It reveals that (43.3%) of farmers had amount ranging from N601, 000- N800, 000 as their annual income in watermelon production. This indicates that (100%) livelihood assets owned by watermelon farmers helped them to reduce poverty, crimes; militancy, terrorism and reduce over dependency on government among others. The constraints faced by the watermelon farmers are lack of improved variety of seeds, limited access to credit facilities, preservation and storage facilities and high perishability, transport facilities, marketing information, extension services, pests and diseases. It is therefore, recommended that government and donor agencies should provide alternative sources of income so as to influence participation of farmers into watermelon production. It is also recommended that watermelon processing and storage technologies should be put in place, so as to avoid the incidence of losses.

Keywords; Livelihood Assets, Watermelon, Farmers Production Sokoto.

INTRODUCTION

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) belongs to the family Cucurbitaceae whose centre of origin has been traced to Kalahari and Sahara deserts in Africa (Ereketi and Asa, 2014). From there, watermelon spread to countries along the Mediterranean Sea and even beyond. According to FAO (2017) statistics, China is the world's leading producer of watermelon. The top twenty leading farmers of watermelon produced a collective volume of

approximately 92.7 million metric tons in 2017, of which China produced 75%. Turkey, Iran and Brazil commanded a production share (of the 20 leading farmers) of 4.7%, 3.5% and 2.4% respectively in 2017. Nigeria produced more watermelons in 2017 (139,223 tons) than the leading fresh produce African exporter, Kenya, which produced 66,196 tons and South Africa that produced 77,993 tons (Shubin and Ernst, 2018). African countries like Nigeria and Kenya produced watermelon in commercial quantities. For instance, 139,223 tons and 66,196 tons of watermelon were produced in 2017 in Nigeria and Kenya respectively (Adeoye, et al 2012).

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In Nigeria, watermelon production has increased significantly in the last one decade with the major production areas being located in the Sahel, Sudan and Guinea agro-ecological zones. In recent times, its cultivation has extended down to the forest belts of southwestern Nigeria (Orzolek et al., 2010.). However, the northern fringes of the Sudan and Sahel savanna ecological zones and the shores of the Lake Chad remain the major production areas. In Nigeria watermelon production is confined to the Northern part of Nigeria due to suitability of agro-ecological conditions of the region. (Daily Trust, 2016).

Watermelon production is playing a vital role in reviving the economic activities, poverty reduction and improving the socio-economic status of its farmers. For its nutritious value, watermelon is eaten fresh or used for other purposes. In terms of nutrient composition, it contained 92% water and 8% sugar. It is rich in lycopene, an antioxidant that gives it its characteristic colour (Shubin and Ernst, 2018). Other mineral content present in watermelon are potassium, magnesium, phosphorus, calcium, zinc, iron, and cuprum. Apart from nutrient value, it is an important source of medicine (George et al, 2017). Watermelon production is playing a vital role in reviving economic activities, poverty reduction and improving the socio-economic status of its farmers. As a result of this assertion watermelon is considered the most preferred exotic vegetables produced in large quantities and most consumed cucurbit because of its economic and health values (Adeoye, et al., 2011).

Watermelon is becoming a very important source of income for small scale farmers especially in the semi-arid tropics of West Africa, where it is grown commercially (Produce, 2008). They explain participation as a physical engagement in which farmers hold complete power and are in full control of their program (Ahmadu, et al, 2012). Production and consumption of watermelon are increasing at an alarming proportion worldwide. In Nigeria the crop is gaining ground due to its high economic and nutritional value. The growing awareness of the crop for these attributes influence of livelihoods assets in it production.

Moreover, farmers' participating in watermelon production is a vital factor for its sustainable development because it is critical in coming up with successful development plans. Stanzin et al., (2017) iterated that watermelon is an important source of income for small scale farmers especially in the semi-arid tropic of West Africa (Adekunle et al., 2011). Watermelon production in Sokoto and Kebbi states have dominated small scale farmers that are found in Goronyo, Kebbe, Silame and Shagari local government areas of Sokoto state.

Despite the growing awareness of nutritional, medicinal, economic and commercial value of watermelon in the study area. The productivity remained very low due to some factors that need to be given serious attention in order to ensure full participation of

farmers in its production (Abubakar, 2017). Watermelon supply in Nigeria has not been able to keep pace with population growth. This low production of watermelon calls for a close examination of influence of livelihoods assets in watermelon production. (Adekunle et al., 2011). Ahmad, et al, (2017). Watermelon production has been characterized by some factors which tend to limit full participation of farmers in it production such factors are difficulties in acquiring improved agricultural inputs, handling and knowledge of processing; and other factors affecting watermelon production such as low income, unavailability of storage facilities, pests and diseases (Shubin and Ernst, 2018).

It has been observed that Nigeria has the potentials in terms of land and human resources needed to produce enough watermelon for the country ((Balarane and Oladele, 2012) and (Adewale, 2012). Therefore, previous studies have not made adequate analysis of the influence of livelihoods assets in watermelon production in Sokoto state. This study focus attention to bridge the gap, give room for comparison with other studies. The Objective of the study is to examine the influence of livelihood in watermelon production in Sokoto State. The specific objectives of the study are to describe the socio-economic characteristics of watermelon farmers in the study area; to determine the income level of watermelon farmers in the study area; to identify the livelihood assets of watermelon farmers in the study area and to identify the constraints faced by watermelon farmers in the study area.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Description of the Study Area

This study was conducted in Sokoto State. Sokoto State is located between latitude $11^{\circ}55'N$ to $14^{\circ}00'N$ and longitude $4^{\circ}56'E$ to $13^{\circ}50'E$. The State is bordered to the north by Niger republic, Zamfara State by East and Kebbi State by the South and West (SSGD, 2018). The state comprises 23 Local Government Areas (LGAs). The state covered an area of approximately 75, 000 square kilometers with a projected human population projection of 5, 997,708 (NPC, 2018). Majority of the people in The State are Hausa and Fulani. (Illiya and Baba. 2013). Furthermore, the farming activities in the state are divided into upland and lowland. The upland farming is preferred during the rainy season accounts for most of the agricultural practices, where grains and legumes such as millet, sorghum, cowpea, and groundnut are commonly cultivated. In the lowland practices, less than 15% of the farmers are into Fadama cultivation in which crops such as watermelon, onion, pepper, garlic, cassava and carrot are popularly cultivated (Fatima, 2019). The duration of rainfall in the states is between May to November within the mean annual rainfalls 600mm. However, the duration

of the rainfall in the entire state is usually erratic, associated with periodic drought (Illiya and Baba, 2013).

The dry season starts from October to April, while the wet season begins between May/June. The harmattan which is dry, cold and dust laden wind arrives from December to February. Daily maximum temperature is about 36°C and an average temperature of 28.3°C. During harmattan season, daily minimum temperature falls below 17°C. The warmest months are February to April, where in a day temperature reaches 44°C. Relative humidity is between 15-20% during the dry season and up to 70-75% during rainy season (Iliya *et al.*, 2013). The region's lifeline for growing crops is the floodplains of the Sokoto and Rima river system, which are covered with rich alluvial soils. Local crafts such as blacksmithing, weaving, dyeing, carving and leather working also play an important role in economic life of the people (Abubakar *et al.*, 2012).

Data collection

Both primary and secondary information were used in the study. The set of questionnaire was administered to the watermelon farmers in the study area. And the primary data were also collected with the aid of using FGD's, Likert Scale and pair wise ranking tables. The data collected were based on socio-economic characteristics of the watermelon farmers, income level of the watermelon farmers, and the livelihood assets of watermelon farmers in the study area. The constraints faced by watermelon farmers in the study area twenty watermelon farmers were randomly selected from each 24 villages to obtain a total of 480 watermelon farmers in the study areas.

Farmers annual income realized such as; <N401, 000-N600, 000, N601, 000 - N800, 000, N801, 000- N1, 000,000. Data were collected on Data were also collected on the livelihood assets of watermelon farmers: Natural Assets; Hunting of Wildlife, Earth Dams, Economic Trees, Firewood Making, Family Land, and Community Land. Human assets of the watermelon farmers: Education; Science and vocational related, Art and craft related, Social science, Skills education; Herbalist, Lawyer, Engineering, Pastoralist, Apprentice, Health; Conventional hospital, Traditional medicine, Financial assets of the watermelon farmers: Income from farm, Cash at hand, Income from other jobs, Bank savings, Liquid assets, Pension, Physical assets of the watermelon farmers: Radio, Wall clock, Kerosene, stove, Fan, Spade, Cutlass, Hoe, Television, Generator, Water pump, Handset, Motorcycle, Refrigerator, Bicycle, shovel, Set of cushion, Watering can, Cars, Well, Tricycle, Social assets of the watermelon producer: brother, cousins, aunties; uncle's relatives, access to market, access to school, access to hospital, access to roads.

The constraints faced by watermelon farmers: lack of improve variety of seeds, inadequate credit facilities,

inadequate preservation and storage facilities, Inadequate extension services, pests and diseases, rural urban migration, high perishability of the product, poor road network, inadequate transportation facilities, poor marketing channel.

Data Analysis

The analytical procedures used for achieving the objectives of the study are descriptive statistics (frequency percentage and means Likert scale type, multiple regression analysis, pair wise ranking. Each of the objectives was achieved as follows:

The first, third, objectives were achieved using descriptive statistics. The second objective to determine the income level watermelon farmers in the study area was achieved by using farm budgeting.

The fourth objective to identify the constraints faced by watermelon farmers was achieved by using Pair wise ranking.

PRA tools (Focus Group Discussion using check list, and Pair wise ranking is often used by social scientists, and increasingly by community development workers, as a means of prioritizing or ranking lists prepared by communities (Subedi, 2008).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the watermelon farmers

Sex of watermelon farmers

Table 1.1 indicates that majority of the watermelon farmers (95.4%) are male while only 4.6% of them are female. This is not surprising as females are usually saddled with domestic work, which requires their full participation coupled with the culture in the area. The findings corroborates with Muhammad *et al.*, (2009) who opines that the males dominates agricultural sector as compared to female. This result is in line with the findings of Adeoye *et al.* (2011) reported that male folk dominate watermelon production. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Eric (2007) that the male watermelon farmers earned more income than the female watermelon farmers. Though male invest more than their female counter part they as well earn more than them but certainly the returns from watermelon are higher than those obtained from potato production. This could be the reason why more watermelon farmers in the study area now cultivate watermelon more than they do potato in order to boost income generation.

Age of watermelon farmers

Table 2 shows that Majority of the watermelon farmers (35.2%) falls under the age category of 30- 39 years,

Table 1 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Sex.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Sex		
Male	458	95.4
Female	22	4.6
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table. 2 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Age.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Age		
30-39	169	35.2
40-49	284	59.2
50-59	8	1.7
60 and Above	19	
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 3 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their marital status.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Marital status		
Single	60	12.6
Married	420	87.5
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 4 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Education level.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Education level		
Qur'anic education	219	45.6
Adult education	60	12.5
Primary education	176	36.7
Secondary education	15	3.1
Tertiary education	10	2.1
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

watermelon farmers within this age bracket are considered to be at their active age of participation in watermelon production. This is in line with the findings of U NYES (2004) which reported that the active ages of farmers are between 40-49 years. The age bracket of 30-39 is reported to be (59.2%). This agrees with findings of Adeoye *et al*, (2011) which revealed that young and middle aged individuals who are active and innovative are involved in watermelon production. The implication of this is that watermelon production was carried out mostly by farmers with youthful age.

Marital Status of the watermelon farmers

Table 3 indicates that the marital status of the watermelon farmers. The highest frequency which show

that (87.5%) of the watermelon farmers are married. About (12.5%) of the watermelon farmers are single. It implies that majority (87.5%) of watermelon farmers are married. This corroborates with Olukosi and Alamu (2008) findings that majority of rural work forces are married. This implies that watermelon farmers had family responsibilities and financial commitment. So, watermelon farmers in rural communities engaged in early marriage to raise families to support in farm labour.

Educational level of watermelon farmers

Table 4 shows that (45.6%) of the watermelon farmers are said to have attained Qur'anic education. It also report that (12.5%) to have attained Adult education. The attainment of such level of education can help the

Table 5 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Family size.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Family size		
< 5 families	169	35.2
6-10 families	171	35.6
11-15 families	118	24.6
16-20 families	12	2.5
> 20 families	10	2.1
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 6 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their farming experience.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Farming experience		
1-5 years	19	4.0
6-10 families	120	25.0
11-15 families	232	48.0
16-20 families	-	-
21 and above years	109	22.7
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Table 7 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Occupation.

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Occupation		
Watermelon production	373	77.7
Crop and Livestock production	64	13.3
Petty trading	224	5.0
Civil servant	19	4.0
Total	480	100

Source: Field survey, 2021.

watermelon farmers to easily accept new innovations. This is due to the fact that education plays a very important role among the watermelon farmers as supported by the findings of (Anonymous, 2017). Each watermelon farmer had at least one form of education or the other. This agrees with the findings of Adeoye *et al* (2011) that watermelon farmer has high literacy level in Oyo state.

Family size of watermelon farmers

Table 5 shows that watermelon farmers (35.2%) have 5 persons that live with them as families 35.6% have 6-10 persons, and 20 and above persons as the size of their families. The number of persons in families has positive impact on watermelon production as it increases labour and reduces its cost. This is in line with the findings of Olaniyi and Adewale (2012). Who found that family size of watermelon farmers in the study area were 6-10 persons with highest percentage value of (35.6%). This

agrees with the findings of Adeoye *et al* (2011) which stated that family size of watermelon farmers are large and family members of a rural area form a part of their labour. The implication is that watermelon farmers do not have larger family size in the study area.

Farming experience in watermelon production

Table 6 shows that most of watermelon farmers (48.3%) had 11- 15 years of experience in watermelon production. (22.7%) had a watermelon production experience of 21 years and above. Oladele, (2015) who reported that experience in production is important and it comes with years of practice. The results concur with the findings of Adeoye, *et al* (2011) who reported that average production experience of watermelon is 15 years. The implication is that most of the watermelon farmers do not have long period of production experience. This implies that watermelon production became more popular activity in the global arena in recent years because of its health

Table 8 Distribution of farmers according to their Sources of funds for watermelon production

Characteristics	Frequency	Percent
Watermelon production	420	87.5
Commercial bank loan	27	5.6
Personal savings	339	70.6
Cooperative	30	6.3
Traditional saving	60	12.5
Others	24	5.0

Source: Field survey, 2021.

Multiple responses are allowed

Table 9 Quantity of watermelon produced

Variable	Frequency	Percent
1-5 tons	190	40
6-10 tons	120	25
11-15 tons	45	9.3
16-20 tons	40	8.3
21 -25 tons	35	7.3
26- 30 tons	50	10.4

Source: field survey, 2021.

Table 10 Profit Analysis of Watermelon Production

Frequency	Average income	Average total cost	Average profit
170	₦200, 000	₦60, 000	₦140, 000
110	₦400, 000	₦140, 00	₦260, 000
30	₦600, 000	₦180, 000	₦420, 000
45	₦800, 000	₦240, 000	₦560, 000
40	₦1, 000,000	₦350, 000	₦650, 000
35	₦2, 000,000	₦420, 000	₦1, 580,000
50	₦2, 500,000	₦720, 000	₦1, 780,000
Total 480	₦7, 500,000	₦2, 110,000	₦ 5,390,000

Source: field survey, 2021.

benefits and higher income generation.

Occupation of watermelon farmers

Table 7 indicates that majority of the watermelon farmers (77.7%) were engaged in other crops and livestock production as their occupation while 5.0% are into petty trading, 4.0% are civil servants. The implication of these findings is farmers of watermelon as their occupation have greater chance of participation in its production. This agrees with the finding of Muhammad et al (2009) who reported that watermelon farmers who choose watermelon production as their primary occupation have greater chances of participating in its production. This is line with findings of Adeoye et al 2007 that watermelon has now become a very prominent crop being planted by majority of farmers in recent years and have become a very important source of income for small scale farmer in most rural communities in Nigeria. (Ajewole, 2015) This implies that most of the watermelon farmers produce

watermelon to diversify from their primary occupation to make ends meet and only cultivate watermelon to generate more income. The study also indicates that very few of the respondents were civil servants, with (4.0%) earning an annual income. This is similar to the findings of Wald, (2014) who reported that the major occupation of the respondents in his study area is farming (90%) whereas 5% of the respondents are civil servants with 2.5 and 2% being traders and agro-processors.

Income level of watermelon farmers

Sources of funds for watermelon production

Table 8 shows that majority of the watermelon farmers 87.5% source their funds from watermelon production while 5.6% acquire their funds from commercial bank loan. This is in line with the study of Stanzin and Lobzing (2017) reported that the major occupation of the watermelon that their main source of funds was its

Table 11 Results of multiple regression analysis on relationship between the socio-economic characteristics and factors influencing participation watermelon farmers.

Variable	Coefficient	SD err.	P-value	Decision
Gender	1.513	.732	.0039**	Significant
Age	-.002	.262	.994	Not significant
Marital status	-.021	.632	.974	Not significant
Educational Level	.633	.177	.000***	Significant
Family size	-.067	.198	.735	Not significant
Farm Size	.237	.236	.002**	Significant
Farming Experience	.336	.178	0.004**	Significant
Occupation	.226	.245	0.001***	Significant
R-Squared	0.88			
F-value	77.43			

Source: field survey, 2021. P < 0.001***; P < 0.05**

Noted: multiple responses are allowed

Table 12 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Natural assets

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Hunting of Wildlife	60	12.5
Earth Dams	15	3.1
Economic Trees	219	45.5
Firewood Making	176	36.7
Family Land	232	38.0
Community Land	120	25.0

Source field survey, 2021.

Note: multiple responses were allowed

production whereas only 70.6% obtained their funds from personal saving. As a result, most of watermelon farmers get their funds from 6.3% cooperative and 12.5% traditional saving, followed by crop production whereas the non-participants obtain their funds mainly from others 5.0%.

Productivity of watermelon (Quantity of watermelon produced)

Table 9 shows that majority 40% of respondents they produced 1-5 tons of watermelon while, 25% produced 6-10 tons of watermelon. The result also shows that 9.3 % produced 11-15 and 8.3% produced 16-20 tons of watermelon. The result revealed that 7.3% produced 21-25 tons of watermelon and 10.4% produced 26-30 tons of watermelon.

Table above shows the relationship between socio-economic characteristics and influence of livelihood assets of watermelon farmers. The results reveals that age, marital status and family size are Socio-economic characteristics with negative coefficient are not significant while gender, educational level, farm size, production experience occupation and education level are the Socio-economic characteristics with positive coefficient and are found to be significant at P < 0.05. The negative coefficient implies that the socio economic characteristics of watermelon farmers and Influence of livelihood assets

of watermelon farmers are not influenced by age, marital status, and family size. Meanwhile, the positive coefficient implies that the socio economic characteristics of watermelon farmers and influence of livelihood assets watermelon farmers are influenced by gender, farm size, farming experience educational level occupation. This is in agreeing with the study of Davis, (2005). Farmer's educational level tends to participate more than those that are laggards. This is in agreeing with the study of Abubakar, (2006). In relation with gender, farm size and occupation bear significant relationship at 1 % and 5%. The results imply that the influence of livelihood assets of watermelon farmers have a significant relationship between the gender, farm size and education level. This is in agree with the study of Delgado, et al (2011), this indicates that the more the occupation of its farmers, farm size and education level in production, the more they the income generated. The finding there for indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected because not all the Socio-economic characteristics indicate significant relationship. This is in agreeing with the study of Diker, et al, (2011). The results further indicate that socio- economic characteristics such as gender, farm size, farming experience. This is consistent with the findings of Ebojei et al, (2012), they find out that increasing in educational level and farm size are expected to increase crop output of fadarna farmers in Northern Nigeria. This is consistent with the findings of Olaniyi and Adewale (2012) in their

Table 13 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Human Assets

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Science and vocational	232	48.0
Art and craft related	120	25.0
Social science	128	26.7
Skills education		
Herbalist	118	24.6
Lawyer	10	2.1
Engineering	12	2.5
Farmer	171	35.6
Apprentice	232	48.0
Health		
Conventional hospital	373	77.7
Traditional medicine	405	84.4

Source field survey, 2021.

Note: multiple responses were allowed.

Table 14 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their financial assets

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Income from farm	208	43.3
Cash at hand	16	3.3
Income from other jobs	171	35.6
Bank savings	60	12.5
Liquid assets	22	4.6
Pension	3	0.6

Source: field survey, 2021.

Note: multiple responses were allowed.

findings report that there is no significant relationship between ages, family size and output for garden egg production in Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. The coefficient of farm size is positive and statistically significant at ($p < 0.05$), which means that the formulated alternative hypothesis is accepted.

LIVELIHOOD ASSETS OF WATERMELON FARMERS

Natural Assets of watermelon farmers

Table 12 shows that majority of the natural assets accessed by watermelon farmers include family land 48.0% Economic trees 45.6%, firewood making 36.7% and community land 25.0%. However, the least natural assets accessed by the watermelon farmers were: hunting of wild life 12.5%, and Earth dam 3.1%. The findings implies that most of the watermelon farmers are rural dwellers and have access to land and other natural assets which can be used for productive purposes to support their livelihood activities (DFID, 2000; Nicol, 2000).

Human Assets of watermelon farmers

Table 13 shows that human assets accessed by

watermelon farmers includes; education and health facilities 48.0%, of the watermelon farmers acquired science and vocational related, 25.0%, of watermelon farmers acquired art and craft, related, 26.7% of watermelon farmers acquired social science related, Skills education, 24.6% of watermelon farmers are herbalist. However, 2.1 % of watermelon farmers are lawyers, 2.5% of watermelon farmers are engineers.35% of the watermelon farmers are pastoralist, 48.0% of the watermelon farmers are apprentice, Conversely, 77.7% of the watermelon farmers used conventional hospital, 84.4% of watermelon farmers used traditional medicine. The findings implies that most of the watermelon farmers are rural dwellers and have access to vocational ,art and craft related which can be used for productive purposes to support their livelihood activities (DFID, 2000; Nicol, 2000).

Financial assets of watermelon farmers

Table 14 shows that; the major financial assets owned by the watermelon farmers were income obtained from farm 43.3%, Income obtained from other jobs 35.6%, and Bank Savings 12.5%, while the least financial assets were liquid assets 4.6%, cash at hand 3.3% and pension 0.6%. The finding shows that financial asset facilitates the ownership of physical asset.

Table 15 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Physical assets

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Radio	405	84.4
Wall clock	352	73.3
Kerosene stove	324	67.5
Fan	208	43.3
Spade	480	100
Cutlass	480	100
Hoe	480	100
Television	232	48.0
Generator	109	22.7
Water pump	479	99
Handset	480	100
Motorcycle	373	77.7
Refrigerator	109	22.7
Bicycle	232	48.0
Shovel	480	100
Set of cushion	64	13.3
Watering can	480	100
Cars	109	22.7
Well	480	100
Tricycle	120	25.0

Source: field Survey, 2021.

Note: multiple responses were allowed.

Physical assets owned by watermelon farmers

Table 15 shows that; the major physical assets owned by the watermelon farmers were 84.4% of the watermelon farmers have Radios, 73.3% of the watermelon farmers have Wall clocks, 67.5% of the watermelon farmers have Kerosene stoves 43.3% of the watermelon farmers have Fans, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Spades, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Cutlasses, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Hoes, 48.0% of the watermelon farmers have Televisions, 22.7% of the watermelon farmers have Generators, 99% of the watermelon farmers have water pump, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Handsets, 77.7% of the watermelon farmers have Motorcycles, 22.7% of the watermelon producer shave Refrigerators, 48.0% of the watermelon farmers have Bicycles, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Shovels, 13.3% of the watermelon farmers have Set of cushions, 100% of the watermelon farmers have watering cans, 22.7% of the water melon farmers have Cars, 100% of the watermelon farmers have Wells, 25.0% of the watermelon farmers have Tricycle.

The findings implies that most of the watermelon farmers have physical assets such as spades, cutlasses, hoes, shovels and wells as a prerequisite for watermelon production which can be used for effective production to support their livelihood activities (DFID, 2000; Nicol, 2000). The summary of the physical asset of watermelon farmers is presented in Table 15 The findings showed that; the most common physical assets among

watermelon farmers in this context are; cutlasses, fans, spades, Kerosene stoves, wall clocks, hoes, radios, television and tables. This implies that, almost all the watermelon farmers owned these assets that represent the basic necessity of livelihood sustainability.

For instance, watermelon farmers need spade and cutlass to help them in farm operations. Another important set of assets available to watermelon farmers were: handset, generator and buildings. It is observed that accumulation of these assets is in line with the livelihood activities of watermelon farmers. The societal needs also prompted the acquisition of these assets. For instance, the epileptic supply of public electricity warrants many people to sort for alternative source of power. In addition, the globalization of economic activities also necessitates the acquisition of mobile phones by watermelon farmers. The result also showed that, the least physical assets owned by watermelon farmers were cars, set of cushions refrigerators, and tricycles. This implies that, almost all the respondents owned these assets that represent the basic necessity of livelihood sustainability. However, it is the cost implication and the need for these assets that reduce its accumulation (DFID, 2000; Nicol, 2000).

Social assets of watermelon farmers

Table 16 shows the type of social assets owned by watermelon farmers in the study area. It resulted that; almost 100% of the watermelon farmers have brothers, cousins, aunties and 84.4% have uncles or relatives. It is

Table 16 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to their Social assets

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Brother, cousins, Aunties,	480	100
Uncle's relatives	405	84.4
Access to market	352	73.3
Access to School	263	54.8
Access to Hospital	60	12.5
Access to Roads	210	73.3
Farmer's Organization	352	73.3

Source: field Survey, 2021.

Note: multiple responses were allowed.

also clear that about 73.3% and 54.8% of watermelon farmers have access to markets and schools respectively. The result further revealed that, 84.4% access to hospitals and 73.3% Farmers organization as wells, 84.4% as access to roads were among the important social assets available for watermelon farmers in the area (Datta, and Singh, 2011). However, the finding shows the importance of social asset towards sustainable livelihood activities of watermelon farmers. Social assets offer mechanisms for the farmers to help each other in terms of need, solve internal conflicts, and thus reducing powerlessness and mitigate adverse effects of immediate social problems (DFID, 2000; Nicol, 2000).

Methods of preservation and storage of watermelon

Table 17 reveals that majority, 95% of the watermelon farmers stored their watermelon under shades, 16% of the watermelon farmers store their watermelon in the Tri-wall fibre containers, 9.6% of watermelon farmers store their watermelon in cartons, and 60% of the watermelon farmers stored their watermelon in indoors at room temperature. Roomcooling, force cooling, hydro cooling, and ice bank cooling are all modern methods of watermelon preservation and storage, Meanwhile, 51% of watermelon farmers preserved their products for some days. About 9.3% of watermelon farmers preserve d their watermelon in cans as fruit salad and 2% of watermelon farmers dry their watermelon (Agbetiameh, 2006).

Interpretation of pair wise ranking of constraints faced by watermelon farmers.

Table 18 constraints are what the watermelon farmers perceive as hindrance or problems that deter them from getting maximum production and profit. The table 18 shows that Pests and diseases are serious constraints faced by watermelon farmers with scored 7 ranked 1st. This could be due to lack of frequent spraying with agrochemicals after (herbicides/insecticides) every rain fall. This is consistent with the findings of Ebojei et al, (2012). This affects production and the quality of product produced. Pests and diseases are one of the critical

constraints in watermelon production systems. This is consistent with the findings of (Joans and Srnreker, 2009) point out that pests and diseases caused by bacteria, nematodes, fungi and viruses cause significant losses of watermelon in Nigeria. Watermelon is also particularly sensitive to pest pressure and is therefore subject to intensive application of chemical or organic.

The misuse of pesticides has raised concerns about health hazards linked to intoxications resulting in morbidity, deaths and environmental pollution. This is consistent with the findings of Shaftel, (2012). Again, Adeniji et al. (2012) assert that key factors affecting farmers' are pest and diseases Apart from excessive insects and disease damage, other constraints that prevent farmers from achieving potential yields are unavailability of quality seed, the use of un adapted varieties, low soil fertility, postharvest losses and the lack of appropriate cultural practices. Table 18 shows that high perishability (fruit spoilage) scored 6 ranked 2nd are one of the constraints faced by watermelon farmers in as another problem that hinders their production. Watermelons products re quire special handling they are often too perishable.

This is consistent with the finding of Ekerete, et al, (2014). Hence, marketing of watermelon products involve a large number of participants in the channels of distributions which includes assemblers, transporters,wholesalers, retailers and other actors that add one value or the other. This is consistent with the findings of (Agbo and Usoroh, 2015). Tshiala, and Olwoch, (2010). Table 18 reveals that lack of improved varieties of seeds scored 5 ranked 3th as most pressing challenge faced by farmers. FAO, (2005). Lack of improved seeds is one of the constraints faced by watermelon farmers is another problem that hinders their production. Table 18 reveals that lack of adequate storage scored 4 ranked 4th is one of the constraints faced by watermelon farmers is another problem that hinders their production accounts for divergence between national food security and watermelon farmers food security. FAO, (2017). Even if the total production of watermelon seems adequate at the aggregate level, it will not lead to significant improvement in watermelon security unless the watermelon is available for

Table 17 Distribution of watermelon farmers according to preservation and storage.

S/n	Variable	Frequency	Percent
1	Under shade	458	95
2	Tri-wall fibre containers	78	16
3	Cartoons	46	9.6
4	Indoor storage	289	60
5	Room cooling	-	-
6	Forced air cooling	-	-
7	Hydro cooling	-	-
8	Ice bank cooling	-	-
9	Freezer	245	51
10	Canning	45	9.3
11	Drying	10	2

Source: Field Survey, 2021.

Note: Multiple responses were allowed

consumption at the right time and in the right form. FAO, (2011).

Whereas food must be consumed on a daily basis; production has a different specific time profile. Storage and processing are critical in ensuring that the commodities produced at particular period are for consumption whenever and wherever they are required. FAO, (2012). A significant quantity of products harvested in Nigeria perishes due to lack of storage and processing facilities. Simple, efficient, and cost effective technologies for perishables, such as watermelon and other vegetables, are not as highly developed in the country compared to the storage technologies for cereal grains and legumes. This is consistent with the findings of Farayola, et al., (2014). Consequently, post-harvest, storage losses are very high, approximately 40% for perishables, compared to cereal grains and pulses at about 15%. This is consistent with the findings of (Saha and Ernst, 2018). Ibrahim and Sada (2015).

Traditional storage facilities have certain deficiencies, including a low elevated base giving easy access to rodents, wooden floors that termites could attack, weak supporting structures that are not moisture-proof. Table 18 reveals that inadequate credit is another constraint as the result reveals that 87.5% the inadequate amount of credit scored 3 ranked 5th it is significant in reducing the watermelon production of the farmers. Farmers who are far away from rural banks are less likely to demand credit from the banks and vice versa. This is consistent with the findings of (Abdulhakim and Chemat, 2011). Table 18 reveals that inadequate extension services scored 2 ranked 6th, farmers were not informed by the extension agents to participate actively on watermelon production so as to benefit from credit facilities and other benefits from the associations.

This is consistent with the findings of Fatima, (2019). Farmers were not thought by the extension agents to participate in farmers associations especially in relation to watermelon production which could enable them have access to market outlet, information and interventions by

nongovernmental organizations or probably they were taught but were not convinced. George, et al, (2017). Inadequate extension services were another major problem confronting watermelon farmers in the study areas with. This could be that farmers do not have access to extension agents or services where they get necessary information technically to boost production, they produce little or no yield. This affected their level of production seriously. Table 18 reveals that inadequate transportation facilities scored 1 ranked 7th was one of the constraints faced by watermelon farmers as another problem that hinders their watermelon production.

One of the pressing problems of watermelon production is the lack of adequate transport services at reasonable cost this is consistent with the findings of (Zumbo et al., 2007). Lack of transport services refer to absence of the transport service in important watermelon production, high freight charges due to inadequacy, lack of allweather roads and transport vehicles, unsuitability of the existing transport facilities for the transportation of some produce like fruits, vegetables, eggs, among others, from the rural areas This is consistent with the findings of (Adakaren, 2014). An efficient network of road is vital for effective and efficient agricultural marketing; however, the majority of Nigerian rural roads are in very deplorable conditions thus leading to high cost of transportation and the resultant inefficient marketing performance. This is consistent with the findings of Joan and Smreker, (2009).

Conversely, high transportation was not reported as a major problem at the retail level of the market. The result could be attributed to the fact that majority of the retailers buy and resale in the same market and as such incur less transportation and handling costs within the markets. The results also show that cost of produce was a major constraint faced by the retailers in the marketing of watermelon. These are consistent with the findings of (Khadim and Akram, 2013). This could be attributed to the high cost of transportation, handling costs and other marketing costs incurred by the wholesalers which are transferred to the retailers. Table 18 reveals that

Table 18 Distribution of farmers Pair wise ranking according to the constraints faced in watermelon production.

S/no	Constraints no.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Score	Rank
1.	Lack of improve variety of seeds	X	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	5	3 rd
2.	Pests and Diseases		X	2	2	2	2	2	2	7	1 st
3.	High perishability of the produce			X	3	3	3	3	3	6	2 nd
4.	Inadequate storage facilities				X	4	4	4	4	4	4 th
5.	Inadequate credit facilities					X	5	5	5	3	5 th
6.	Inadequate extension services						X	6	6	2	6 th
7.	Inadequate transportation facilities							X	7	1	7 th
8.	Poor marketing information								X	0	8 th

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Note: Multiple responses were allowed

marketing information scored O ranked 8th is one of the constraints faced by watermelon farmers is another problem that hinders their production. Marketing information of watermelon products, play a critical role in meeting the overall goals of economic development. This is consistent with the findings of (Botlhoko and Oladele, 2013), particularly among watermelon marketers in developing countries. This is consistent with the findings of (Xaba and Masuku 2012).

However, Wald, (2014) argues that deficiencies in rural infrastructure services result in poor functioning domestic markets with little spatial and temporal integration, low price transmission and weak international competitiveness. This is consistent with the findings of Orzolek, et al, (2010) in their study notes that prominent constraints of watermelon marketing among the agricultural marketers are: lack of access to credit, lack of access to storage facilities, lack of market information, poorly developed village markets, poor producer prices, high perishability of produce, low patronage, inadequate access roads and high transportation costs. Other major constraints to agricultural marketing includes lack of storage facilities, low educational levels of the marketers, poor agricultural extension services, lack of financial support.

This is consistent with the findings of Xaba and Masuku, (2012) in Swaziland also opined that lack of information regarding prices, inadequate local markets, lack of bargaining power, excess of intermediaries also constituted marketing constraints among agricultural marketers. This is consistent with findings of Singletary, et al., (2011) who further reported that socio-economic factors of the marketer such as training, marketing experience, age, level of education and farmers family size; lack of access to good roads, price risk and uncertainty, poor communication also constitute major constraints to efficient marketing.

CONCLUSION

Watermelon production is dominated by farmers in their active ages of 30-39 years. Income is significantly

influenced by gender, educational level, farm size, farming experience, and occupation. Most of the watermelon farmers have considerable experience in watermelon production using their personal saving and obtain about 11-15 tons every season. Due to certain socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers, low usage of agricultural inputs and farm machinery is still evident in their low level of output produced. The profit margin is quiet appreciable. The majority of farmers uses improved seeds and applies manure as sources of nutrient in watermelon production. The majority of the farmers were largely subsistence since agricultural inputs were very expensive.

To increased agricultural production is dependent on the inputs used by the farmers. However, the study concluded that farmers long participated in watermelon production had learnt to planned and allocate resources in its production and watermelon enterprises had seen as an important source of income and employment in the study area.

Hence, watermelon farmers need to avoid incurring their inputs indiscriminately and should form cooperative society as an alternative source of income so as to better their production.

In conclusion, the findings of this study, shows that livelihood assets owned by the watermelon farmers have increased in a greater level. It was also concluded that achieving increased watermelon production in the study area it dependent on the preservation and storage of the products Therefore, Watermelon marketing was profitable and thus a veritable means of livelihoods and poverty alleviation. However, lack of storage technologies, lack of modern implements and high cost of inputs are the constraints faced by watermelon farmers. Livelihood assets owned by watermelon farmers in this context had addressed the rate of unemployment in the study area.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made:

It is recommended that watermelon farmers should mobili

zed their members so as to influence them to participate more than ever before irrespective of their socio-economic characteristics differences.

Watermelon farmers should be educated on how to plan and allocate budget in its production.

Watermelon farmers should form cooperative as alternative sources of information and income so as to influences its production.

There is need for more capacity building from time to time to update farmers about watermelon production activity in the study area.

Further research should be conducted to include more characteristics and duration to replicate the study and validate the current findings.

It is recommended that watermelon farmers should increase their human assets by educating their members of the community; this will enable their skills to be improved and thus have the capability to work and produce financial asset and other assets that will enhance a sustainable livelihood outcomes.

It is recommended that watermelon farmers should improve their participation in social activities such as farmer's organizations, cooperatives etc., this builds membership and trust and also enables farmers to help others solve their problems and as well share knowledge skills and ideas.

It is recommended that watermelon farmers should have information and understand the marketing channel of watermelon products

It is recommended that watermelon farmers should provide modern preservation and storage facilities.

It is recommended to develop and improve indigenous watermelon variety by the research agencies to increase yields, qualities and quantities and make watermelon variety more resistant to pests and diseases and adaptable to climatic condition.

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